

THE ROLE OF POETRY IN ENHANCING NATURE EDUCATION FOR SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT IN NIGERIA

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Abstract

Poetry has always been associated with intensity of emotions expressed in literary form with a sense of rhythm and beauty. This study identified poetry as a valuable tool which can be used in promoting nature education for sustainable economic growth and environmental safety in Nigeria. It also identified poetry as a valuable tool which can be used in climate change education across various campuses, companies, communities and cities in Nigeria. Through literature review and participant observation, this study identified how poetry is being used innovatively in nature education in Nigeria to achieve the sustainable development goals. This paper is significant as it explores new opportunities and benefits in the innovative use of poetry for nature education thereby enhancing climate resilience for sustainable development.

Keywords: Education, Nature, Nigeria, Poetry, Sustainable Development.

1.1. INTRODUCTION

Nature, in the broadest sense, is the physical world or universe. "Nature" can refer to the phenomena of the physical world, and also to life in general. The study of nature is a large part of science (Ducarme, Frédéric; Couvet & Denis, 2020). Although humans are part of nature, human activity is often understood as a separate category from other natural phenomena. The idea of 'nature' is at the very core of science, considered as its flagship and deepest link with human societies. Nature can be defined as the phenomena of the physical world collectively, including plants, animals, the landscape, and other features and products of the earth (Callicott and Ames, 1989). Whereas in the Greek and Roman view of the world, even the gods were part of nature, in a monotheist context God transcends nature, and so does the Man, as he is created at the image of God (Callicott and Ames, 1989). *Nature education is generally named with similar terms, for example, place-based education, environmental education, outdoor education, and environment-based*

education” (Louv, 2008). According to Keleş et al. (2010), nature education is aimed at recognizing nature in natural environments and making use of what nature offers as educational subjects, materials, and tools. In nature education, it is essential to use what nature offers as educational materials (Keleş, 2011). Nature education is based on the idea that students learn by living and dealing with authentic examples and models offered by nature so that learning will be more permanent and pleasurable. Studies on nature education have attracted attention as a result of field studies conducted in England and Australia (Strom,1980). Nature Education is therefore vital for preparing communities and institutions across Nigeria for climate change impacts and to learn how we can adapt and mitigate effectively. Poetry with its psychological benefits has been discovered as valuable tool which can be used to help students and teachers in the various educational institutions in Nigeria and beyond to appreciate the beauty of nature, understand the impacts of climate change and to learn the adaptation and mitigation strategies for sustainability.

1.2. METHODOLOGY

This paper examined current progress with “the role of poetry in enhancing nature education for sustainable development in Nigeria” through existing literature review and data collection from relevant agencies. The main purpose of this research work was to survey theoretical backgrounds and previous studies on above subject matter and the current progress with the implementation of these innovative strategies in Nigeria.

1.3. UNDERSTANDING POETRY

A poem is a piece of writing in which the words are chosen for their beauty and sound and are carefully arranged, often in short lines which rhyme. Top universities around the world are beginning to discover the science of poetry and its psychological benefits as a valuable universities tool for global sustainability. John Mcauliffe highlighted that reading poems can be so fascinating: science and wonder combined which can help individual interests shape their studies of the sciences and engineering(Cochlin,2012).There is no doubt, therefore, that poetry can be used as a valuable tool to convey the message of nature’s beauty and blessedness in schools, universities and institutions around the world in a very profound way. Poetry is beauty and beauty attracts. Poetry has a unique way of communicating to the listeners and readers the message of hope, beauty and love that enables them to seek creatively ways to preserve our planet from global warming. Poetry for nature education education with its healing and therapeutic benefits can be used with mothers, fathers, children, and adolescents; battered women, the elderly, the depressed, the suicidal; those living with terminal illness, the bereaved, those with HIV, the mentally ill, and even hurricane victims and soldiers returning from war who suffer post traumatic stress. Poetry can give students a healthy outlet for surging emotions(Anabaraonye,Nji & Hope,2018). Reading original poetry on nature aloud in class can foster trust and empathy in the classroom community while also emphasizing speaking and listening skills that are often neglected in high school literature classes. Nature poetry can help in language development, creative language skills, creativity, writing skills, self expression, and in the development of natural rhythms while helping to educate the community on nature’s beauty and blessedness. Poetry is fun and exciting and beautiful and can be used effectively for nature education for sustainable development in Nigeria (Anabaraonye,Nji & Hope,2018).Nigerian Universities should therefore not be left out in this discovery of poetry as a valuable tool for nature education. Furthermore, there is a great need for scientists, researchers, lecturers and students in the Universities to conduct further research on valuable tool of poetry and its innovative use for nature education to enhance sustainable development in Nigeria.

2.1. NATURE EDUCATION FOR SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT

Consequently, in accepting the reality of climate change, an aggressive nature education programme is key in militating the obvious impact of climate change on man. Nature education will enable the community to see the beauty and blessedness of nature and how to preserve it thereby enhancing climate resilience in Nigeria. Furthermore, an environmental health advocate will respect nature, help feed the hungry and also engage in nature education for sustainable development. The United Nations Environment having declared the theme “Time For Nature” for World Environment Day 2020 presents a challenge and an inspiration (UNESCO, 2020). The theme challenges us to take treasure in the beauty of nature, take action using both science and arts to inspire global actions towards environmental sustainability (UNESCO, 2020). Thus, the Benjy Poetry And Music Global Concepts organized an event on the 5th of June, 2020 being the World Environment Day 2020 featuring composing and reciting of inspiring climate change poetry by outstanding poets, seminars by climate change professionals and networking opportunities for the youths in Anambra State (Anabaraonye, 2020). The impact of the World Environment Day 2020 event was profound as many of the participants attested through their testimonials which were published online. This reiterates the psychological benefits of poetry and the key role poetry can play in educating individuals, communities and institutions on nature’s beauty and blessedness.

2.2. UNDERSTANDING CLIMATE CHANGE

The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change defines climate change as statistical variations that persist for an extended period, typically decades or longer. The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) defines adaptation as the “adjustment in natural or human systems to a new or changing environment. Adaptation to climate change refers to adjustment in natural or human systems in response to actual stimuli or their effects, which moderates harm or exploits beneficial opportunities. Various types of adaptation can be distinguished, including anticipatory and reactive adaptation, private and public adaptation, and autonomous and planned adaptation (IPCC 2001). Climate mitigation is any action taken to eliminate or reduce the long-term risk and hazards of climate change to human life, property and the society. The International Panel on Climate Change defines mitigation as: “An anthropogenic intervention to reduce the sources or enhance the sinks of greenhouse gases” (GGW, 2018). Climate change poses an immediate and long-term threat to our environment, our people and our planet. Renewable energy would be a promising solution for promoting sustainable development, as well as for addressing climate change, by reducing environmental impacts, enhancing energy security, and providing various developmental co-benefits, such as job creation and capital investment in green industry (ADB, 2014). We have discovered through literature review and participant observation that poetry can be used in a creative and innovative way to teach at various communities and institutions in Nigeria about the benefits of nature and its role in achieving sustainable development. The Benjy Poetry and Music Global Concepts is one of the new companies in Nigeria which of study and research work on climate change education, adaptation and mitigation. This has also engineered the writing of climate change poems to help promote the right attitudes and behaviors needed to safe-guard our environment. According to Victor Pinchuk, a Ukrainian businessman and philanthropist, “Art, freedom and creativity will change society faster than politics” (Pinchuk, 2001). Through the Project Green educational blog: www.projectgreeninitiative.wordpress.com which features articles and poems on climate change adaptation and mitigation for global sustainability, the Benjy Poetry And Music Global Concepts seeks to educate communities and institutions on climate change adaptation and mitigation for global sustainability. Below is one of the nature education poems advanced by the Benjy Poetry And Music Global Concepts.

2.3. POEM “TIME FOR NATURE”

**Nature's voice spurns a rebirth
Nature's choice is clean and green
Feel and enjoy her sweet scent
It's a beautiful world we live in.**

**Nature's voice calls for hope and health
Nature's choice is peace and progress
Our heritage of wits and wealth
Nature's gift to be judiciously harnessed.**

**It is time for nature to be nurtured
Nature is a precious gift from Divine
A precious gift to be treasured
Time for nature! It is time!**

**Nature's voice calls for caution and care
Nature's choice is relish and cherish
Both plants, animals and humans are dear
Refuse to be foolish and selfish**

**Nature's voice we surely can hear
Nature's choice is beauty and grandeur
The health of the planet is our desire
It is time! Time for nature!(Anabaraonye,2020)**

3. RECOMMENDATIONS

1. It is our recommendation that the immense benefits of poetry should be well recognized and used as valuable tools in nature education across primary, secondary and tertiary institutions in Nigeria for global sustainability.
2. Nature poetry should be included in the curricula for both primary schools, secondary schools and even our Universities because of the many psychological benefits which we have listed above.

3. Nature poems and songs should be regularly featured in special radio and television programmes, jingles, social media like youtube, linkedin, facebook and twitter, etc. Apart from providing entertainment, they also provide education on environmental issues to the community.
4. Environmental leadership summits and specialized climate change seminars where nature poetry can be presented by nature professionals and environmentalists across various communities and institutions in Nigeria. This can be done monthly or annually which will in turn enable us to achieve our sustainable development goals.
5. Our youths should be encouraged towards creativity and excellence in acquiring relevant artistic skills in poetry which can be channeled towards nature education for sustainable economic growth. This has the capacity to reduce unemployment and poverty among the youths in Nigeria.

4. CONCLUSION

Our students in the Universities across Nigeria both Undergraduate and Postgraduate must be well educated on the issues of climate change and encouraged to deploy their skills and talents which should be used effectively to help overcome the environmental and economic challenges facing the world today. Through this study, it is clearly highlighted that poetry can be used as a valuable tool in nature education to enable campuses, companies, communities and cities across Nigeria to enhance climate resilience thereby achieving sustainable development.

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Data Availability Statement: The qualitative data utilized for this study will be made available upon reasonable request.

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